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1. Introduction

EOSC EDEN WP1 task 1.2 "Definition of Core Preservation Processes and Metrics for Re-Use Fitness of information objects" is split into two main areas:

- A. Definition of requirements in core trustworthy digital long-term preservation processes
- B. Definition of metrics for re-use fitness of information objects

Milestone 1.2 marks a first public release of work on task B: The definition of Metrics for Information Object Re-Use Fitness. Task B was described in the project proposal as:

Information object re-use fitness will be defined via generic metrics such as the FAIR principles as well as digital preservation metrics such as file format sustainability criteria, significant properties, file format validity and metadata completeness (descriptive, technical, and administrative metadata). A strong focus will be placed on technical digital preservation metrics relating to file formats. T1.2 will liaise with the EOSC FAIR Metric and Data Quality TF for additional metrics to be considered. Preservation risks as well as suitable mitigation strategies will be assigned to each level. The metrics will be passed to WP2 as requirements and to T1.1 for stakeholder validation and maximised uptake.

While this first milestone serves as the initial description and delivers a first set of metrics collected from real life examples, these will be refined further throughout the project. In addition to continuing work in T1.2, the metrics will form the basis for guidelines on tiered digital preservation approaches, which will be picked up by T1.1, T1.3, WP2 and WP3 for stakeholder validation and maximized uptake.

The Re-Use Fitness Model guides all EDEN project outputs. Within T1.2 B, the three quality pillars of the Re-Use Fitness Model serve as overarching **categories** for the work presented in this milestone report (see Figure 1):

Figure 1: The Reuse Fitness Model

For each pillar, quality indicators have been identified. These indicators are designed to be organisation- and system-agnostic, setting good-practice baseline expectations rather than prescribing an idealised model.

This ensures they are flexible, widely applicable, and able to support different institutional strategies and capacities.

The initial set of indicators was adapted from ISO 25012¹ and refined through systematic comparison with institutional policies and process descriptions, professional expertise, and selected standards. The process emphasised consensus, transparency, and traceability, with all changes documented in collaboratively used indicator and metric candidate lists..

Metrics are domain-specific implementable measurements of the indicators adapted to the discipline contents and file formats. However, agreed upon consensus on metrics within domains currently do not exist. Instead, implemented metrics can be found in policy and process descriptions of organisations, for example in CoreTrustSeal certification documentation or collection development policies. These implemented or witnessed metrics vary in conciseness—from actually measurable to rather abstract. While these can be seen as requirements that a TDA has for information object quality, they serve as metric candidates within the scope of EOSC EDEN work presented here. The goal is to validate extracted implemented metrics against stakeholder requirements and in particular domain commonalities in follow-up work to this milestone.

This report summarizes the methodology used behind developing and describing Metrics for Information Object Re-Use Fitness; lists a first set of indicators that guide metric definition; and shows how they link to implemented metrics extracted from organisational practice documentation. This collection of reference requirements as metric candidates form a basis for future work on testing and defining domain-specific metrics.

2. Underlying Notions

A core output of EOSC EDEN will be the Re-Use Fitness model (see Figure 1)—a framework which will help stakeholders identify which objects are candidates for long-term digital preservation, based on use, benefit and quality. The framework is therefore closely linked to acquisition, and aims to guide initial identification, appraisal and selection, as well as on-going re-appraisal. While identification describes the process of (proactively) seeking out, collecting or receiving objects, appraisal describes the process of determining archival value. Selection is a process that builds on the outcomes of appraisal and identifies objects that are to be preserved. Since quality is therefore determined during the appraisal process, it is directly linked to the metric work as an underlying concept. The second concept we expand on in this section is that of data quality itself.

2.1. Appraisal

Within the digital preservation lifecycle, appraisal is a key strategic function, where qualities of potential deposits are identified. These qualities inform the assessment of whether potential deposits warrant acquisition and ongoing stewardship. Appraisal may include evaluations on different levels of granularity, ranging from object-focused and organisational capability assessments, up to an analysis of potential future uses relating to larger themes, such as disciplines or countries. In practice, appraisal often is an interactive

¹ ISO/IEC 25012:2008 Software engineering - Software product Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) - Data quality model

process, involving multiple stakeholders. It requires coordination with potential donors, depositors, owners, data subjects, and record creators to ensure data quality and support optimal lifecycle management. Appraisal also supports informed decision-making about the allocation of preservation resources by assessing the significance, documentation quality, and potential future use of digital objects. Appraisal decisions are inherently linked to a TDA's Designated Community, as well as the intended preservation timeframe, which may range from short-term access needs through to long-term preservation goals, spanning decades or centuries, as reflected in the findings of the T1.1 survey. Discipline-specific retention practices may also include iterative reappraisal as part of active preservation, as developed by the EOSC Long-Term Data Retention Task Force (LTDR TF) in Retention (Re)Appraisal – Iteration Logic (RRAIL).

The following definition for appraisal was agreed upon within the project. It applies to all TDAs regardless of content, discipline or domain:

Appraisal is a function that every Trustworthy Digital Archive (TDA) undertakes to decide whether digital objects will be accepted into its holdings or not. During appraisal the TDA evaluates the qualities of potential deposits by assessing their characteristics against a set of indicators that should be made transparent in the form of a written policy. The outcome of this evaluation provides evidence on the expected level of investment in the retention, curation and active long-term preservation of digital objects, and guides acquisition, transfer, and ingest. Reappraisal may be performed throughout a digital object's lifecycle and as retention periods expire, leading to digital objects being passed through the appraisal function again.

Appraisal is not an objective process, as it involves making decisions about what should be preserved and why, for how long, and at what level of investment. It is therefore inherently shaped by organisational priorities, stakeholder needs, the anticipated future use by the Designated community, as well as resources available to a TDA. As in the case of the Core Preservation Processes, appraisal cannot be reduced to a standardised procedure, but requires situated knowledge and professional evaluation. Nonetheless, some aspects of appraisal can be abstracted into generally applicable indicators, as developed and described in T1.2. These indicators articulate the various facets of a digital object that may be considered when performing appraisal.

However, the identification of appropriate metrics, responsibilities, workflows, and methods for appraisal cannot be generalised, so they require an individual assessment by each organisation against its needs and mission. Depending on the mission and priorities of the TDA, some indicators may constitute primary or secondary appraisal values, while others may not be considered relevant at all.

It is up to the role responsible for appraisal to decide which indicators are considered relevant (or not), and how to measure and assess them accordingly. To ensure that decisions are transparent, consistent, and accountable, the identification, selection and implementation of appropriate metrics should be specified and made transparent in the form of a written policy. Transparency in appraisal decision making also enables institutions to demonstrate their compliance with key principles such as FAIR, CARE and TRUST by ensuring that the collection development and preservation decisions are transparent, ethically justified and aligned with community best-practices.

2.2. Data Quality

Task 1.2-B focuses on the characteristics of digital objects that may affect their usability and preservability—as well as their usefulness, discoverability, etc. in the context of appraisal. The objective is therefore to determine which properties of the objects condition:

- The producer or initial user’s ability to use the object for its original function;
- The TDA’s ability to fulfill its preservation mission;
- The re-user’s ability to use the object for any secondary functions.²

The concept of “data quality” is therefore central here. We have reused a definition proposed in the report *Towards a Data Quality Framework for EOSC*³, which in turn derived it from the ISO 8000 standard:

‘the degree to which a set of **inherent characteristics** of data **fulfils requirements**’⁴

The reader is referred to this reference document for a comprehensive review of the concept of “data quality” in the professional literature. However, the following two subsections will highlight the interpretive challenges that the application of this definition to a long-term preservation context poses.

2.2.1. Inherent characteristics

The term “inherent characteristics” warrants closer examination. The aforementioned *Towards a Data Quality Framework for EOSC* report notes that most of the reference documents it analyses distinguish between “data-dependent” characteristics (i.e., inherent ones) and “system-dependent” ones. The ISO 25012 standard⁵ distinguishes between data-dependent quality dimensions (accuracy, completeness) and system-dependent ones (security, portability).⁶ Similarly, the collaborative article “International community guidelines for sharing and reusing quality information of individual earth science datasets”⁷ distinguishes between scientific and technical assessments – based on data-dependent characteristics – and stewardship and custodianship assessments – based on system-dependent aspects.

While T1.2-A focused on processes, namely the Core Preservation Processes, the metrics work in T1.2B focuses on the data. We will therefore concentrate on dimensions determined either wholly or partially by data-dependent characteristics. This distinction sets the present deliverable apart from other initiatives dedicated to assessing research data quality, notably the FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics.⁸ The latter document proposes 17 metrics for evaluating data quality based on either data-specific or

² Although this report focuses on the first two points – since reuse for purposes other than the original one will be the subject of Task 1.3 of this work package – the topic is not entirely absent, as certain indicators reflect the historical, secondary value of digital objects.

³ Lacagnina, Carlo, Romain David, Anastasija Nikiforova, et al. *Towards a Data Quality Framework for EOSC*. 9 January 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7515815>.

⁴ Emphasis was added by the authors of this report.

⁵ International Standards Organisation. *Software Engineering – Software Product Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) – Data Quality Model*. International Standard ISO/IEC 25012. Version 2008. Published December 2008. <https://www.iso.org/standard/35736.html>.

⁶ However, certain dimensions – such as confidentiality, accessibility, and efficiency – can be affected by the inherent properties of the data as well as by the system in which they are accessed and stored.

⁷ Peng, Ge, Carlo Lacagnina, Ivana Ivánová, et al. ‘International Community Guidelines for Sharing and Reusing Quality Information of Individual Earth Science Datasets’. Preprint, 16 April 2021. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/xsu4p>.

⁸ Huber, Robert. *FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics*. Version 0.8, 18 March 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15045911>.

system-specific metrics. Metric FsF-A1-02M (“Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol”) serves as a prime example: from the user’s perspective, it matters little whether a drop in service quality stems from the data itself or from the processes involved. However, if one adopts the perspective of a Trusted Digital Archive (TDA) deciding whether or not to ingest a digital object into its collections – as this report does – the distinction between data-dependent and system-dependent quality becomes relevant.

Indeed, TDAs – particularly those with a long-term preservation mandate, such as libraries and archives – recognize that they will outlast multiple migrations of their storage and access systems. This does not mean that a TDA’s current capabilities are irrelevant during the appraisal process; on the contrary, technical specifications, in particular the file format policy, are often heavily influenced by the TDA’s existing capabilities. However, it does imply that TDAs must envision the lifecycle of a digital object as extending beyond the specific software and hardware tools available to them at any given time.

Another aspect that may shape a different understanding of the inherent characteristics of digital objects is the interventionism of TDAs regarding the digital object and the concern for its authenticity. Indeed, some of the research data repositories that we considered in this report can be involved earlier in the creation process, or even participate actively in it. Specialized repositories dedicated to preserving a specific type of content – such as [UniProt](#) – often employ expert curators capable of addressing quality issues (e.g., missing units for numerical values, failure to use an ontology or controlled vocabulary). In contrast, TDAs involved in long-term preservation – particularly libraries and archives – are generally less specialized and/or must cover a wider range of fields and disciplines. Consequently, they tend to apply a stricter definition of data authenticity. In such cases, they rarely need to assess “quality” (in the common sense of evaluating an object against universal criteria to classify it as good or bad). Instead, TDAs of this type often operate under specific mandates that base the acquisition of objects on their provenance or the characteristics of their creator. Archives tend to prioritize the historical and evidentiary value of digital objects – qualities that can be compromised if the object undergoes any modification, whether intentional or not. Consequently, they generally do not aim to contribute to the development or improvement of the object; instead, the priority is to collect and preserve it in a form strictly faithful to the original – hence the use of skills and tools traditionally associated with digital forensics.

2.2.2. Fulfilling Requirements

The definition cited above establishes that “data quality” is characterized by the extent to which an object’s characteristics meet an agent’s requirements. This agent is either the digital object’s end-user or the TDA. In the context of this report – and given the focus on the appraisal function – we will concentrate on the requirements set by the TDAs, in the hope that these reflect, at least in part, the requirements of end-users.

The scope of the metrics encompasses the full meaning of “data quality” – covering both utility (fitness-for-purpose) and warranty (fitness-for-use). In other words, the metrics must address both the question “Is the digital object useful?” and the question “Is the digital object usable?” Added to these are questions regarding the characteristics that make an object more or less costly to preserve. “Durability” is not an inherent characteristic of a digital object, and no format is durable by nature. However, there are digital objects that, due to their characteristics – including their file format – require varying levels of investment in terms of human effort, hardware, and financial resources.

The study of TDA requirements conducted by the task group (and described below) reveals that the criteria most frequently cited by TDAs include a diverse range of indicators, which can be categorized as follows:

- Dimensions linked to the institution's mission as defined by its governing body: "Creator," "Geographic relation," "Provenance," etc.
- Traditional quality dimensions defined by data quality frameworks, such as "Accuracy", "Consistency", "Completeness", etc.
- Dimensions related to risks affecting the TDA's ability to correctly render digital objects: "Validity," "Sanity," "Protection measures," etc.
- Dimensions related to positive impact and social utility for end-users: "Public well-being," "Scientific recognition," etc.

Another observation made by the group is that the consequences of a mismatch between an object's characteristics and TDA requirements are generally overlooked in policy documents. However, it is likely that failures to meet requirements will be handled differently by the TDA: some will indeed result in the outright rejection of the digital object, while others will lead to negotiations with the producer or trigger preservation action by TDA staff.

3. Definition and Scope of Indicators and Metrics

3.1. Structuring the Concept of Data Quality in T1.2-B

Studies proposing reference models for data quality assessment establish a hierarchical structure ranging from the most general concepts to more operational considerations that can be assessed – sometimes quantitatively. The seminal article by Wang and Strong on data quality⁹ identifies 179 data "attributes," aggregating them into 20 dimensions that are, in turn, categorized according to four principles: "Relevancy," "Accuracy," "Representation," and "Accessibility." These categories have been adopted in numerous subsequent studies to characterize dimensions or indicators developed from specific perspectives. It is striking to note that the approach used to construct this reference framework is bottom-up. Indeed, the surveys conducted by the authors identify the most granular elements—the attributes—which are then grouped into dimensions and categories through a classification process that allows for a certain degree of interpretation.

Some other reference documents address only one of these hierarchical levels: the previously cited ISO 25012 standard defines 15 "dimensions." Others, such as the *Data Quality Guidelines*¹⁰, propose a three-level structure:

- At the highest level, the four FAIR **principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable);
- The intermediate level consists of relatively generic "**indicators**," which correspond roughly to the level of precision of the "dimensions" defined by the ISO 25012 standard.
- These "indicators" cannot be measured directly and must be broken down into more precise and granular elements – prescriptive, measurable "**metrics**." For example, the "Completeness" indicator is calculated by measuring the values of the metrics "Number of null values," "Number of empty fields in metadata," and "Data set identifier resolves to a digital object."

⁹ Wang, Richard Y., and Diane M. Strong. 'Beyond Accuracy: What Data Quality Means to Data Consumers'. *Journal of Management Information Systems* 12, no. 4 (1996): 5–33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07421222.1996.11518099>.

¹⁰ Publications Office of the European Union. *Data.Europa.Eu Data Quality Guidelines*. Publications Office of the European Union, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.2830/333095>.

The structuring of this latter document into principles, indicators and metrics appeared particularly well-suited to the work involved in task T1.2-B. It had nevertheless to be adapted to the peculiarities of the EDEN project, in the following way:

- At the highest level, the three pillars of the "Re-use fitness" model are employed: Contextual Data Quality, Technical Data Quality, and Metadata Quality.
- A significant number of indicators have been detailed for each of these pillars.
- Metrics have been drawn from several policy documents drafted by various TDAs.

It should be noted that, like the Wang & Strong article mentioned earlier, the approach was also bottom-up: the group began by identifying candidate metrics from the requirements set out in policy documents, then aggregated them into indicators, which were in turn classified under one of the pillars of the Reuse Fitness model. The full methodology is detailed in the next section.

Figure 2 presents this particular structure, with one example indicator and metric per category. The following subsections will detail each level of the structure in question.

Figure 2. Structure of the T1.2-B outcome

3.2. Level 1: Categories

The Reuse Fitness Framework, developed for the needs of the EDEN project, defines a quality typology based on three pillars, defined as follows:

- **Contextual Data Quality** investigates digital objects at the semantic level. It comprises their significance based on their informational and evidential value. Evaluation is based on qualitative criteria (such as evidentiary, informational, associational, research value etc.) and assessment depends on discipline-specific knowledge about the object and its process of creation.
- **Technical Data Quality** investigates digital objects at the logical level. Evaluation is based on the intrinsic properties of its underlying data structures (such as files, folder hierarchies, streams, or file systems).
- **Metadata Quality** investigates the width and depth of accompanying information describing the digital object. Evaluation is based on the quality of its textual, generally structured, description intended for discovery and management. This pillar is an essential means that ties together the contextual and technical data quality pillars by documenting and linking individual bits of information to ensure meaningful preservation over time.

In addition, the pillars are held together by two horizontal axes as follows:

- **Preservation objectives / designated community needs** correspond to the mission of a TDA as specified in its mission statements, collection development policies, preservation policies, etc. These objectives should be defined in close collaboration with the designated community to ensure that information is preserved in a meaningful and understandable manner – this aspect of the Reuse Fitness Framework has not been developed yet.
- **TDA capabilities** correspond to the financial, human and technical resources a TDA has at its disposition – this was the focus on T1.2-A “Core Preservation Processes”.

Although the FAIR principles seem like obvious candidates for categorizing data quality, they have significant short-comings compared to the "Reuse Fitness" model. While the four dimensions of FAIR are certainly fundamental to the end user, they do not allow for the inclusion of a significant number of requirements specified by TDAs – such as those relating to the discipline represented by the digital object, its provenance, the characteristics of its creator, and so on. Similarly, "technical" quality requirements – which focus primarily on file format characteristics – cannot be easily categorized without forcing the model. The Reuse Fitness model shall close this gap, functioning as a high-level model which incorporates quality dimensions that determine a TDA's ability to preserve the digital object, alongside those that facilitate end-user applications.

3.3. Level 2: Indicators

The indicators represent the quality dimensions that TDAs consider when appraising a digital object. They are generic and reflect the diverse characteristics of a digital object that a repository evaluates to determine whether it belongs in its collections.

The indicators were developed by compiling and aggregating the requirements and recommendations found in the policy documents studied by the group. Although some are better suited to certain types of content than others – for example, "Compliance with style conventions" applies primarily, though not exclusively, to digital objects consisting of computer code – most are broadly applicable to a wide range of digital object types.

The indicators suggest that the appraisal process must take into account contextual quality, technical quality, and metadata quality. They also suggest relationships between these dimensions, such as:

- Between a generic contextual dimension like "Completeness" and technical dimensions that specify its application, such as "Data Integrity" and "Self-Sufficiency";
- Between a data quality dimension like "Data Integrity" and the metadata quality dimension that enables its assessment and documentation – specifically, "Technical Metadata."

3.4. Level 3: Metrics

The indicators represent generic dimensions of digital object quality. They are designed to apply to diverse contexts and the widest possible range of digital objects; consequently, they are not actionable or operationalizable in their raw form. Each indicator must therefore be broken down into more precise requirements corresponding to specific characteristics of the digital objects. In the EDEN project, these requirements are termed "metrics." These metrics are domain-specific, implementable measurements derived from the indicators. Given the vast diversity of institutional contexts and digital object types,

producing a universal list would be an overly ambitious undertaking. The current list of metrics is more designed as a representative set of requirements expressed in policy documents published by TDAs, reflecting the diverse appraisal criteria TDAs use to evaluate the quality of the objects submitted to them.

It is nonetheless important to bear in mind that these metrics correspond solely to the requirements that TDAs agree to adopt and publish. It is reasonable to assume that other, less openly acknowledged criteria play a role in the complex equations leading to the acceptance or rejection of digital objects. For instance, the indicator Monetary Value – which is represented by only one metric, in a document outlining the various types of value considered by archivists – is nowhere presented by an institution as an official appraisal criterion. Yet, it is likely that certain collecting institutions in the cultural sector do indeed use it – if only because of mechanisms such as Acceptance in lieu (under British law)¹¹ or “dation” (under French and Canadian law).¹²

The metrics were derived from requirements articulated by TDA or from recommendations issued by authoritative bodies in a given field, such as the Federal Agencies Digital Guidelines Initiative (FADGI). Furthermore, the policies and procedures underpinning these metrics vary in their level of detail, ranging from strategic to tactical or operational.¹³ Consequently, the requirements themselves vary in precision; they may take the form of broad programmatic directions or specific prescriptions regarding the characteristics of the files representing digital objects. The working group embraces this diversity of requirements. We believe there must be alignment between strategic and operational levels, just as file format policies must be linked to the collection objectives defined in development policies.

A number of more precise metrics are meant to be applied to a specific data type. Those metrics are classified into a typology inspired by the content categories developed by the Library of Congress for its “Sustainability of Digital Formats” site.¹⁴

Furthermore, readers will note that the metrics may be redundant, insofar as they correspond to a requirement expressed by a specific TDA in specific terms. Here again, the decision was made to provide all references to a given requirement, as it was deemed useful to consider the various formulations adopted by the TDAs. For the same reason, the metrics may contradict one another. The EDEN project therefore does not endorse the metrics; responsibility for them lies with the organization that issued them.

Consequently, the metrics presented in the attached table are not intended to serve as a list of requirements to be implemented as-is for all TDAs. Instead, they can be used in several ways, including:

- As a means of understanding the concept of “quality” as envisioned by the TDAs at the time this report was published;
- As an illustration of the meaning of the indicators, in cases where their necessarily concise definitions might leave too much room for interpretation;
- As a source of inspiration for TDAs wishing to develop their own collection development and quality policies.

¹¹ *Wikipedia*. ‘Acceptance in lieu’. 15 May 2025.

https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Acceptance_in_lieu&oldid=1290556807.

¹² *Wikipedia*. ‘Dation en paiement’. 5 April 2026.

https://fr.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Dation_en_paiement&oldid=234825143.

¹³ This classification of digital preservation policies and procedures is drawn from the document ‘Digital Preservation Policy of the KB’. National Library of the Netherlands, August 2024.

<https://www.kb.nl/en/file-download/download/public/9222>, p. 6.

¹⁴ “Content Categories” in *Sustainability of Digital Formats*, website maintained by the Library of Congress at https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/content/content_categories.shtml.

For further information on the development of the metrics, please refer to subsection 4.2, “Requirements Extraction,” and for information on their use, to section 6, “Use Cases.”

4. Methodology for Indicators and Metrics Identification

Metrics were gathered and described by T1.2 members between November 2025 and June 2026. The work followed a practice-led qualitative approach, combining international standards with institutional policies and documentation.

4.1. Identification of Sources

The initial list of sources was compiled by TIB. Subsequently, additional sources were identified and collected by the remaining project members. This was done primarily based on the analysis of the initial resources, which consisted mainly of CoreTrustSeal (CTS) documents, as one of the criteria (R08 Deposit and Appraisal) is particularly focused on the appraisal criteria that in turn referenced additional documentary sources to support their assertions, particularly collection development and file format policies. From the long list of CoreTrustSeal-certified organization files, a sample was selected, targeting in priority research institutes. Certain other institutions were included because of their discipline, in order to achieve better representativeness.

Concerning technical quality, the first sources that the group considered were the sustainability criteria of file formats, which identify categories of risks weighing on digital objects according to their format. To extend the scope to more precise sources, which do not exclusively consider preservation risks but also integrate important quality requirements for end users, recommendation documents on data formats by type of content have been added, in particular the *Recommended Format Statements* published by Library of Congress.¹⁵

Project members were additionally encouraged to identify supplementary sources, such as appraisal policies, preservation policies, and other guidelines and recommendations. The sources were categorized as high and lower priority; the higher priority sources included:

- CTS documents, with a particular focus on requirements R0, R08 (deposit and appraisal), RT10 (quality assurance), R02 (rights management) and R04 (legal and ethics),
- D1.1¹⁶ and D3.1¹⁷ deliverables,
- Recommended Format Statements published by the Library of Congress,
- Collection development policies / statements / strategies, file format policies and file format sustainability criteria published by different organisations.

¹⁵ Library of Congress. ‘Recommended Formats Statement’. Library of Congress. Accessed 29 June 2026. <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/resources/rfs/TOC.html>.

¹⁶ Molloy, Laura, Micky Lindlar, Maria Benauer, Helene N. Andreassen, Karl Presser, and Märkälä Anu. *EOSC EDEN D1.1 - Overview of Identification, Selection and Appraisal Practices for Long-Term Preservation of Data*. 19 December 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.17984753>.

¹⁷ Andreassen, Helene N., Anna-Lena Flügel, Terje Klemetsen, et al. *EOSC EDEN D3.1 - Report on Discipline Requirements and Needs*. 1 July 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15789260>.

A shared commonality of analyzed sources were frequently referenced collection development and file format policies, in particular in responses to the EOSC EDEN survey on appraisal practices (D1.1) and the CTS documents. Once identified from the original source, they were added to the list and further analyzed.

The sources were collected into a spreadsheet, which identified each source by its label, owner organisation and its type, an acronym (short name), document type, and URL where the source was available. The sources were categorised by document type, and the categorisation was specified by the T1.2 B extended task group. The sources were subsequently assigned to project members for further analysis and requirements extraction, and once this was completed, the source was marked as processed by means of a completion status indicator.

A total of 121 sources were collected into the spreadsheet. Of those, 79 sources were selected for further analysis and requirement extraction. The selection was made by the task group.

4.2. Metrics Definition

The analysis was conducted as a bottom up approach, meaning the extraction and definition followed the following chain: quality requirements were extracted from source documents, quality requirements were captured as implemented metrics, in an iterative process implemented metrics fed into indicators. First, each selected source document was assigned to one task group member, who extracted requirements and recommendations on inherent data quality from it. The working spreadsheet was used to document all the findings. Each requirement was kept traceable to its source – identified by a short name together with a direct quotation of the relevant passage – and was categorised either by data type, e.g. images, structured text, etc., or as a generic requirement. The member then rephrased each requirement into a concise form. A total of 618 requirements were extracted, 403 of them generic.

Quality requirements were assigned implemented metrics labels that reflect the group member's interpretation of the requirement as found in the source. Wherever possible, the terms "must," "should," and "may" have been used when the level of obligation associated with the requirement could be determined.

Finally, each metric was mapped to one of the three RUFit pillars (contextual data quality, technical data quality, or metadata quality), and an indicator was assigned to it. The whole process was carried out in the working spreadsheet, which progressively recorded, for every requirement, its property, its unit and level(s) to reach, its RUFit pillar, and the associated candidate indicator.

Metrics are published in a separate document. Please note that the EDEN project does not endorse these requirements, the responsibility for their content remains with the institution that issued them.

In addition, the concept of data properties was explored for metrics. Data properties were understood as the specific characteristic of the data that the requirement tests (its "data property that the requirement is testing"). Where a requirement was measurable, two further attributes were recorded – the unit in which the property is measured, and the level(s) to reach, that is, the minimum value the property must attain to fulfil the requirement. Thus, the following data was extracted from the requirements:

- Property
- Unit
- Level(s) to reach

These properties are what link requirements to indicators, because they condense each requirement into a specific value and domain. At this early stage the properties were only lightly curated, yielding an initial list of

221 unique values. The units and levels to reach are intended as guidelines from which institutions can develop their own measurable appraisal requirements. Since data properties were only loosely curated in the task group and require further in-depth analysis, they are not included in the milestone report. Possibilities for inclusion in the information object re-use fitness framework will be explored further.

4.3. Metrics Curation & Definition of Indicators

An initial separate list of indicators was created at the beginning of this task. These indicators were divided into three separate categories corresponding to the Reuse Fitness model pillars: technical data quality (TDQ), contextual data quality (CDQ) and metadata quality (MDQ). In the first iteration, v0.1, 18 indicators for TDQ were added. ISO/IEC 25012 provided an initial source for the indicators and their definitions. This initial list quickly proved to be insufficient, as the analysis of the TDA policies revealed that the diversity of the criteria, in particular those on CDQ such as provenance and characteristics of the creator, could not be evaluated through the lens of ISO 25012 quality dimensions. In the case of CDQ, additional standards and terminologies from Records and Archives Management were consulted to enhance the and specify the list of indicators. Bringing in additional perspectives, however, also created additional challenges by introducing terminological duplication. Since ISO 15012 and ISO 15489 describe equivalent concepts but describe them by differing terminology, a mapping of corresponding notions was created, where appropriate.

Analysing the extracted requirements in the working spreadsheet provided a gap analysis and feedback for expanding the set of indicators. As a requirement was analysed, it was either mapped to an existing indicator or to a potential new one. New suggested indicators were analysed, and if approved by the group, added to the separate list of indicators.

Some difficulties in the alignment of metrics to indicators arose from the lack of justification for the requirement in the source text. In some cases, this justification can be easily inferred – for example, it is obvious that a recommendation to consistently use UTF-8 character encoding aims to enhance the understandability and machine-readability of a text-based object. In other instances, however, the rationale behind a requirement is far less apparent – at least to non-specialists in the field. This lack of justification is common regarding file format recommendations or policies; few organizations explain their preference for specific formats in sufficiently precise terms.¹⁸

The suggested indicators and their definitions were further defined and discussed in the working group. In total, the indicator definition iterated through five agreed upon versions. Contextual data indicators were added in the second version, and metadata quality indicators were agreed upon in the fifth installment of the indicators list.

In addition to ISO standards, CODATA RDM terminology and SAA terminology were used as sources for compiling the list of contextual data quality indicators and their definitions.

¹⁸ There are some notable exceptions, particularly the NARA Risk Matrix (National Archives and Records Administration, digital-preservation, GitHub repository available at <https://github.com/usnationalarchives/digital-preservation>) or the Catalogue of File Formats for Archiving (KOST-CECO, Catalogue des formats de fichiers pour l'archivage, available at <https://kost-ceco.ch/cms/formats-de-fichiers.html>).

5. Indicators

The following subsections present the indicators classified according to the pillars of the Re-Use Fitness model. As will be reiterated throughout this document, the following list of indicators aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the selection criteria used by TDAs; however, not every indicator is relevant to every TDA or every type of digital object. It is the role of a collection development policy to determine which indicators apply and the way they should be assessed.

5.1. Contextual Data Quality (CDQ)

5.1.1. Considerations on Contextual Data Quality

Contextual Data Quality (CDQ) investigates digital objects at the semantic level. It assesses the extent to which a digital object is sufficiently embedded within its intellectual, organisational, and disciplinary context to allow for interpretation and reuse. Evaluation of CDQ is usually based on qualitative criteria with assessment strongly depending on discipline-specific knowledge about the object, its process of creation, and anticipated usage cases.

Contextual data quality investigates in particular two aspects of data quality:

- When contextual data quality meets the TDA's preservation intention and the needs of its designated community, the objects are **useful**;
- When contextual data quality meets the TDA's capabilities, the preservation of the digital object is **attainable**, i.e., achievable within a reasonable and sustainable level of resource input.

The definitions for the indicators of CDQ are informed by established terminology and conceptual frameworks from multiple sources such as relevant ISO standards from Research Data Management (RDM) and Records Management, the CODATA Research Data Management Terminology¹⁹, the Society of American Archivists (SAA) Dictionary of Archives Terminology²⁰, principles like FAIR,²¹ CARE²² and TRUST²³, and other scientific literature as referenced. Where appropriate, definitions have been adapted to align with EDEN's internal conventions and terminology. For indicators where no suitable existing guidance was available, EDEN-developed definitions were formulated based on underlying principles and theories from Archival Studies.

As part of T1.2, it was decided to build upon archival theory and Theodore Schellenberg's distinction between primary and secondary value in particular.²⁴ These notions are commonly employed as a notion for appraisal within government archives, and consider the long-term value of objects through the lenses of both the immediate usefulness and purpose to its creator as well as its continuing value for the designated

¹⁹ CODATA Research Data Management Terminology <https://vocabs.ardc.edu.au/viewById/685>

²⁰ Society of American Archivists (SAA) Dictionary of Archives Terminology <https://dictionary.archivists.org/>

²¹ D. Wilkinson et al., 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship', *Sci Data*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 160018, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.

²² S. R. Carroll et al., 'The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance', *Data Science Journal*, vol. 19, p. 43, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.5334/dsj-2020-043.

²³ D. Lin et al., 'The TRUST Principles for digital repositories', *Sci Data*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 144, May 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7.

²⁴ Schellenberg, T. R. 1956. *Modern archives: principles and techniques*. University of Chicago Press. p. 133.

community of the TDA. To determine long-term value, Schellenberg distinguishes between evidential value, documenting the functions and activities of the creator, and informational value, reflecting the information and knowledge contained within the object itself. Together, these concepts emphasize that the long-term reuse potential of digital objects depends not only on their content but also on the preservation of their provenance, creation context, and relationships to other objects.²⁵

Whereas Schellenberg's appraisal framework evaluates objects according to their anticipated secondary value for future users, our analysis revealed that the identified requirements primarily articulate qualities that focus on enabling long-term reuse in the first place by highlighting principles such as accessibility, understandability, and reusability. In this way, they align with frameworks like FAIR and OAI, and focus more on the operationalisation of long-term usability, as implied by Schellenberg's notion of secondary value, but do not discuss the assessment of secondary value

The reuse-centred perspective of most sources led to challenges for the classification of legal and ethical indicators, as they frequently articulate desired outcomes for data reuse rather than archival functions or responsibilities. For the differentiation and specification of indicators, both approaches were mapped as follows (see table 1).

Table 1- Legal and ethical indicators

Object	Right holder	Focus	Legal field	Purpose	Indicator
Copyright	Data Creator/Owner	Data	Proprietary rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protection of rights - Institutional control - Claim of commercial interests 	CDQ-018 Intellectual property and Ownership
Licenses					
Sensitive data that represent peoples, nations and communities such as Indigenous data	Community represented in the data	Value-based relationships	Collective rights	Group interest	CDQ-004 Collective benefit ²⁶
Sensitive data that represent information in the interests of national security, the maintenance of public peace, order and security, or in the economic	Society			Societal interest	CDQ-024 Public wellbeing

²⁵ See "Informational value" in *Dictionary of Archives Terminology*, Society of American Archivists, available online at <https://dictionary.archivists.org/entry/informational-value.html> (accessed on June 30 2026).

²⁶ See Carroll, Stephanie Russo, Edit Herczog, Maui Hudson, Keith Russell, and Shelley Stall. 'Operationalizing the CARE and FAIR Principles for Indigenous Data Futures'. *Scientific Data* 8, no. 1 (2021): 108. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-00892-0>.

or financial interests of a self-governing body					
Personal identifiable data	Individual represented in the data	Individual	Individual rights	- Harm prevention - Consent	CDQ-013 Data protection & confidentiality
Other types of data that are considered sensitive based on moral and ethical assumptions	-	Value-based relationships	Individual and collective commitment to voluntary standards	- Societal interest - Harm prevention consent	CDQ-015 Ethical Responsibility & Stewardship

Another key finding from the indicator design is that contextual data quality (CDQ) indicators are rarely binary in nature. Instead, they typically take shape along a continuum, reflecting varying degrees to which a given quality is present or can be assessed. The formulation of “the degree to which...” as employed for many indicators takes this particularity into consideration.

Moreover, CDQ operates on multiple layers and heavily depends on context. For example, Completeness relates to the integrity of an object as a whole in terms of all components being present. Authenticity, by contrast, captures whether an object can be demonstrated to be what it purports to be, therefore focusing on provenance and integrity over time. A similar classification was employed to the indicators “Uniqueness” and “Originality”. Whereas the originality of an object is tied to the disciplinary context of an object, “Uniqueness” relates to the outstanding contribution of an object within any other given context. As such, it is closely tied to “Redundancy” which assesses the data distribution and production practices associated with research. This indicator must not be confused with technical duplication – addressed by TDQ- 024 ‘Singularity’ –, but analyses the recordkeeping habits of the creator, and whether information is kept in multiple locations and formats. Such an approach aligns with the archival understandings of context, provenance, and aggregation, where duplication may carry interpretive significance regarding institutional or creator practices.

5.1.2. List of Contextual Data Quality Indicators

Identifier	Label	Short definition	Source
CDQ-001	Accuracy	The degree to which data has attributes that correctly represent the true value of the intended attribute of a concept or event in a specific context of use.	ISO 25012 ²⁷

²⁷ This is synonymous to ISO 15489 which labels it “reliability”: “Records should be created at the time of the transaction or the incident to which they relate, or soon afterwards, by individuals who have direct knowledge of the facts or by instruments routinely used within the business to conduct the transaction.”

CDQ-002	Aesthetics	The degree to which an object has attributes that establish a visual or aural attractiveness, please the senses, and trigger a positive emotional response.	EDEN definition, partially based on SAA Terminology, Aesthetical value
CDQ-003	Authenticity	An authentic record is one that can be proven a) to be what it purports to be, b) to have been created or sent by the person purported to have created or sent it, and c) to have been created or sent at the time purported	ISO 15489
CDQ-004	Collective Benefit	The degree to which data and metadata represent confidential information that belongs to peoples, nations, and communities (at the collective and individual level), their resources and environments.	EDEN definition, partially based on Operationalizing the CARE and FAIR Principles for Indigenous data futures Scientific Data
CDQ-005	Completeness	The degree to which subject data associated with an entity has values for all expected attributes and related entity instances in a specific context or use.	ISO 25012 ²⁸
CDQ-006	Compliance with Scientific Good Practices	The degree to which data stems from scientific projects that adhered to the foundations of valid scientific work, such as honesty of scientists towards themselves and others, and integrity in the pursuit of truthful knowledge.	EDEN definition based on the Guidelines for Ensuring Good Scientific Practice and Dealing with Scientific Misconduct of the Technische Informationsbibliothek and Procedural Principles
CDQ-007	Conformance with Domain-Specific Protocols	The degree to which data adheres to voluntary standards and specifications, such as ontologies, protocols or	EDEN definition partially based on CODATA, Conformance

²⁸ This is synonymous to ISO 15489 which labels it “integrity”: “The integrity of a record refers to its being complete and unaltered. It is necessary that a record be protected against unauthorized alteration.”

		analytical methods, usually in a defined information domain.	
CDQ-008	Consistency	The degree to which data has attributes that are free from contradiction and are coherent with other data in a specific context of use.	ISO 25012
CDQ-009	Content Type	The discipline-specific typology used to categorise a digital object based on its form, function, or domain-specific usage.	EDEN definition
CDQ-010	Creation Stage	The stage of a digital object within its lifecycle, as defined by its level of processing and validation (e.g., raw, internally processed, externally published).	EDEN definition
CDQ-011	Creator	The characteristics of the agent(s) who created the digital object.	EDEN definition
CDQ-012	Credibility	The degree to which data has attributes that are regarded as true and believable by users in a specific context of use.	ISO 25012
CDQ-013	Data Protection and Confidentiality	The degree to which the rights of individuals or subjects being represented in data and metadata are clarified according to legislated or otherwise broadly accepted norms and policies for preservation and access.	EDEN definition partially based on CODATA , Confidentiality
CDQ-014	Discipline	The relationship of the digital object to a specific branch of scientific knowledge.	EDEN definition
CDQ-015	Ethical Responsibility and Stewardship	The degree to which ethical and moral principles are embedded in both data creation practices	EDEN definition, partially based on CODATA , Data Ethics

		and ongoing archival stewardship. This also includes any corresponding practices, such as the use of data in algorithms, artificial intelligence, or in policy development, which have the potential to positively or negatively impact individuals, groups, or society.	
CDQ-016	Evidence	The degree to which a digital object supports an argument or a legal case and functions as a proof of facts.	EDEN definition, partially based on SAA Terminology, Evidence
CDQ-017	Geographical Relationship	The relationship the digital object bears to a geographical entity.	EDEN definition
CDQ-018	Intellectual Property and Ownership	The degree to which the property status of the digital object (including ownership, copyright and licenses) are clarified and allow for the measures required for preservation and access.	EDEN definition
CDQ-019	Language	The characteristics of the spoken or written human communication system(s) used in the digital object and its metadata.	EDEN definition
CDQ-020	Level of Documentation	The extent to which all associated metadata, data dictionary, description of methods and instruments used to collect and process the data, and other supporting data (such as duplicate sample results, replicate analyses, percent recovery, etc.) are supplied alongside the data, with the purpose of providing the full context in which the data were created.	EDEN definition, partially based on CODATA , Documented data

CDQ-021	Monetary Value	The degree to which the fair market or auction value of the object justifies its retention and preservation.	EDEN definition partially based on SAA Terminology, Monetary Appraisal
CDQ-022	Order	The degree to which the arrangement of data and metadata reflects its original order and contextual relationships, and allows for preservation and access with reasonable effort.	EDEN definition
CDQ-023	Originality	The degree to which a scientific discovery provides subsequent studies with unique knowledge that is not available from previous studies.	Shibayama, S., Wang, J. (2020). Measuring originality in science. <i>Scientometrics</i> 122, 409–427. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-019-03263-0
CDQ-024	Public Well-Being	The degree to which data and metadata contains confidential or sensitive information requiring protection because of the interests of national security, the maintenance of public peace, order and security.	EDEN definition
CDQ-025	Provenance	The characteristics of the origins, custody, and ownership of an object or collection, usually referring to the individual, family, or organization that created or received the objects in a collection.	EDEN Definition partially based on SAA Terminology, Provenance
CDQ-026	Redundancy	Whether a digital object exists in identical or equivalent form elsewhere across systems or locations, including use cases such as multiple contextualisations of the same object, hybrid data management, etc.	EDEN definition

CDQ-027	Reproducibility	The degree to which the efforts associated with the replication of the results of a study using the same input data and procedures used by the original investigator are achievable and reasonable.	EDEN definition, partially based on CODATA , Reproducibility
CDQ-028	Scientific Recognition	The degree to which data has gained recognition within the scientific community through citation, reuse, or other forms of advancements.	EDEN definition
CDQ-029	Societal Impact and Significance	The degree to which data and metadata holds an added value to society and the understanding of human history.	EDEN definition
CDQ-030	Temporal Relationship	The relationship the digital object bears to a particular point or period of time.	EDEN definition
CDQ-031	Topic	The subject(s) and themes addressed by the digital object	EDEN definition
CDQ-032	Understandability	The degree to which data has attributes that enable it to be read and interpreted by users, and are expressed in appropriate languages, symbols and units in a specific context of use.	ISO 25012
CDQ-033	Uniqueness	The degree to which a digital object holds a distinctive and non-substitutable position or function within a specific context.	EDEN Definition, partially based on SAA Terminology, Archival nature

5.2. Technical Data Quality (TDQ)

5.2.1. Considerations on Technical Data Quality

Technical Data Quality investigates digital objects at the logical level. Evaluation is based on the intrinsic properties of its underlying data structures (such as files, folder hierarchies, streams, or file systems). Unlike contextual quality, which is associated with functional requirements, technical quality is often linked to non-functional requirements.²⁹ In other words, contextual quality defines whether an object is useful, whereas technical quality determines whether it is usable.

Technical data quality investigates in particular two aspects of data quality:

- When technical data quality meets the TDA's preservation intention and the needs of its designated community, the objects are **usable, re-usable and interoperable**;
- When technical data quality meets the TDA's capabilities, the digital object is **preservable**.

To a large extent, technical quality requirements are derived from documents describing the sustainability criteria for file formats.³⁰ These documents are excellent sources for identifying risks associated with digital objects. Indicators starting with the term "Format" suggest that the characteristic of the digital object is directly inherited from its format, i.e., its assessment can be made by identifying the digital object's format. In other cases, a specific assessment must be made – for example, TDQ-022 'Sanity' is assessed by CPP-007 'Virus Scanning'.

As previously mentioned, file format policies are often limited to a list of preferred formats without justification. Consequently, it is difficult to assess the reasons why TDAs favor specific formats; these reasons may stem from objective criteria such as expressiveness, compactness, or transparency, but they may also relate to the TDAs' current capabilities or even the legacy of existing practices and systems. For this reason, requirements specifying one or more accepted file formats without further detail were systematically excluded.

It should also be noted that sustainability dimensions – both environmental and economic – are not included as indicators per se. Indeed, indicators are based on the inherent characteristics of digital objects. Just as there is no such thing as an inherently "durable" digital object, there is no such thing as a "sustainable" digital object. However, certain characteristics of digital objects (such as size, format, or organization) can affect the effort required to ensure their preservation.³¹

Depending on the TDA's selection policy, technical quality criteria can influence the decision of whether or not to appraise a digital object. For instance, some TDAs may reject a digital object solely because it fails to comply with the preferred format policy, is invalid according to a specific validation tool, or contains a virus. Other TDAs adopt a more nuanced stance, expressing preferences while still accepting objects deemed useful despite technical quality flaws. In such cases, these flaws – which may indeed pose risks to the TDA's

²⁹ See "Fitness-for-use vs. fitness-for-purpose", in Lacagnina, Carlo, Romain David, Anastasija Nikiforova, et al. *Towards a Data Quality Framework for EOSC*, op. cit., p. 15.

³⁰ A good example of these criteria is provided by the "Sustainability factors" page on the *Sustainability of Digital Formats* website, maintained by the Library of Congress and accessible at <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/sustain/sustain.shtml>.

³¹ Similarly, the preservation processes (copying, integrity calculation, storage and access modes, etc.) are system-dependent and can significantly impact environmental and economic sustainability.

ability to correctly render the object in the future – trigger a preservation action³² rather than a rejection. It is legitimate to incorporate technical quality criteria into the appraisal process. However, it is generally preferable for the TDA to bear the burden of technical quality issues and the associated risks, whereas issues regarding contextual quality logically fall to the producer and may justify rejection by the TDR.

Although the development of the metrics followed a sampling approach and makes no claim to comprehensiveness, it seems possible to derive a few quantitative measures based on the approximately 240 metrics related to technical quality. Notably, eight indicators are associated with ten or more metrics, suggesting that they represent the primary concerns of the TDAs (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Technical data quality Indicators with the highest number of metrics

5.2.2. List of Technical Data Quality indicators

Identifier	Label	Short definition	Source
TDQ-001	Accessibility	The degree to which data can be accessed in a specific context of use, particularly by people who need supporting technology or special configuration because of some disability.	ISO 25012
TDQ-002	Amenity	The optional features of an object that improve user experience and reduce friction.	EDEN definition
TDQ-003	Atypical Features	The file content beyond baseline characteristics that could be improperly interpreted by software tools. Examples include multi-image TIFFs, proprietary chunks in WAVE files, etc.	EDEN definition

³² These actions include: normalization to a managed format while preserving the original, “disinfection,” file repair, technical analysis of the problem’s actual impact, etc.

TDQ-004	Compliance with Style Conventions	The degree to which the digital object complies with style conventions or agreed best practices in coding.	EDEN definition
TDQ-005	Compression	The degree to which the object, or some of its components, have undergone data compression, either lossy or lossless, and if so, by which algorithm.	EDEN definition
TDQ-006	Data Integrity	The object's completeness and intactness according to fixity information, such as manifests and checksums.	EDEN definition
TDQ-007	Dependencies to Software and Hardware Requirements	The software—such as operating systems, libraries, drivers—and hardware dependencies and requirements, particularly if they are uncommon.	EDEN definition
TDQ-008	Format Adoption	The object or file format adoption in the relevant scientific communities, professional sectors, the wider public, and preservation institutions.	EDEN definition
TDQ-009	Format Fitness	The degree to which a chosen object or file format is appropriate for the intended data representation, storage, exchange, and processing.	EDEN definition
TDQ-010	Format Identification Ease and Support	The existence of a specific and sensitive enough pattern that allows for precise object or file format identification and its implementation by format identification tools.	EDEN definition
TDQ-011	Format Life Cycle Status	The object or file format versioning to determine whether it is in an early development stage, mature, or discontinued.	EDEN definition
TDQ-012	Format Specification Availability	The availability of the object or file format specification and its access conditions.	EDEN definition
TDQ-013	Format Standardisation	The maintenance process of an object or file format, in particular if it is ensured by a recognised standard body.	EDEN definition

TDQ-014	Format Structures	The nature of object or file format structures, their transparency and genericity (e.g., ZIP containers wrapping XML data, as opposed to ad-hoc binary data).	EDEN definition
TDQ-015	Granularity	The degree to which an object is composed of discrete components (for example, a mailbox submitted as a single MBOX file or one EML file per email).	EDEN definition
TDQ-016	Impact of Patents	The degree to which the object or file format is subject to patents and licenses.	EDEN definition
TDQ-017	Machine-Readability	The degree to which the object is in a format that is structured enough for automated processing.	EDEN definition
TDQ-018	Media Fragility	The chances that the carrier of a media-based object might break or degrade in the short term.	EDEN definition
TDQ-019	Native Format	The conformity of an object's formal characteristics with another reference object — typically the one distributed to end users.	EDEN definition
TDQ-020	Packaging	The way the object is bundled within file structures for exchange and preservation purposes.	EDEN definition
TDQ-021	Protection Measures	The extent to which the object or the file is protected by technical measures that would prevent future access or preservation actions.	EDEN definition
TDQ-022	Sanity	The absence of malware in the object's bitstream	EDEN definition
TDQ-023	Self-Sufficiency	The extent to which the object is self-sufficient or relies on external material that should be collected and preserved along with it.	EDEN definition
TDQ-024	Singularity	The absence or presence of strict duplicate data in the digital object and/or among the TDA holdings, as verified by checksum calculation or similarity algorithms.	EDEN definition

TDQ-025	Size	The size of the object, in bytes or in number of files.	EDEN definition
TDQ-026	Software Availability for Designated Community Use	The existence of software for regular use by the Designated Community (e.g. rendering, executing and editing), and their availability conditions.	EDEN definition
TDQ-027	Software Availability for Preservation Processes	The existence of software for preservation processes by the TDA (e.g. metadata extraction, file validation, creation of derivatives, file migration), and their availability conditions.	EDEN definition
TDQ-028	Validity	The compliance of the object's data structures against their format specifications.	EDEN definition

5.3. Metadata Quality (MDQ)

5.3.1. Considerations on Metadata Quality

Metadata Quality investigates the width and depth of accompanying information describing the digital object. Evaluation is based on the quality of its textual, generally structured, description intended for discovery and management.

Metadata quality investigates in particular two aspects of data quality:

- When metadata quality meets the TDA's preservation intention and the needs of its designated community, the objects are **findable, reliable and understandable**;
- When metadata quality meets the TDA's capabilities, the digital object is **manageable**.

While Contextual Data Quality and Technical Data Quality describe characteristics inherent to an object, Metadata Quality is concerned with the representation of these characteristics.

Metadata serves as the container of information about an object and, as such, provides the foundation that enables its use. The structure of metadata, the added information chosen to be included, and the form of representation are critical aspects that influence the use of the object by its producer or other users as well as its management by a TDA. A lot of the information typically contained in metadata is not recoverable from the object itself. For example, creator names, the context in which the object was created, or the intent behind its creation may not be embedded directly in the object. In such cases, metadata provides the means to document this information. Deciding which information to include can be regarded as a strategic decision.

Even in cases where information can be extracted from the object itself, it is advisable to store it as metadata. This ensures that the object can be located within the system on the basis of the information. Findability, in turn, is essential for effective object management in a TDA.

Since metadata forms the basis for managing objects in a TDA, different types of metadata support a wide range of use cases. For example, descriptive metadata facilitate discovery, while provenance metadata support the verification of authenticity by documenting the history of changes made to an object.

Table 2 - Metadata Quality Indicators Matrix. Metadata quality dimensions as column headers and metadata type as row headers. Different shades of one colour indicate content/structure

	Accessibility/Usability	Accuracy	Authenticity	Completeness	Consistency
Descriptive	structure	structure	structure	structure	structure
	content	content	content	content	content
Provenance	structure	structure	structure	structure	structure
	content	content	content	content	content
Rights	structure	structure	structure	structure	structure
	content	content	content	content	content
Source	structure	structure	structure	structure	structure
	content	content	content	content	content
Structural	structure	structure	structure	structure	structure
	content	content	content	content	content
Technical	structure	structure	structure	structure	structure
	content	content	content	content	content

The model developed is intended to provide a classification of the TDA quality metrics. To this end, requirements are described in terms of three independent dimensions: metadata quality dimension, metadata type, and structure or content. Each metric may be assigned to a category within any of these dimensions, but it is not mandatory to assign a category in every dimension if this is not possible. At the same time, no more than one assignment is permitted per dimension.

Indicators based on metadata quality dimensions

The quality dimensions describe which inherent property of the metadata is addressed by a metric. They represent general quality characteristics and are independent of specific metadata schemas or individual metadata elements.

The selection is based on the normative definitions in ISO/IEC 25012 for the dimensions of accessibility, accuracy, completeness and consistency, as well as on the definition of authenticity from ISO 15489. These terms were chosen because they describe generally recognized quality characteristics of data and can be applied to the evaluation of metadata.

This model does not aim to cover all the dimensions of data quality discussed in the literature. It is instead intended to be able to describe and classify every analysed metric in a suitably nuanced manner.

Other dimensions proposed in the literature, such as believability³³ or timeliness³⁴, have deliberately not been included. These often relate to the perceived usefulness of the data for specific user groups or to the respective context of use, and therefore do not describe general, inherent properties of the metadata.

The evaluation of Metadata Quality is also not concerned with assessing the actual values of metadata fields. The content of metadata fields is typically evaluated as part of Contextual Data Quality or Technical Data Quality and should therefore be assessed by using the corresponding metrics. Instead, Metadata Quality focuses on the syntactic and structural properties of metadata, albeit with certain limitations.

Other dimensions, such as interpretability and availability, largely overlap with accessibility in the context of metadata, or can be integrated into the selected quality dimensions. The selected quality dimensions therefore fully reflect the quality requirements relevant to the use case, whilst minimizing redundancy as far as possible.

For practical application, the quality dimensions were interpreted as follows:

- **Accessibility/Usability:** The metadata supports the understanding and use of the information described. For human users, this can be achieved through meaningful descriptions or documentation; for machine processing, through standardized, interoperable metadata.
- **Accuracy:** The metadata accurately and correctly reflects the information described.
- **Authenticity:** The metadata enables the traceability of the origin, creation and integrity of the information described, thereby supporting its reliability.
- **Completeness:** All information required for the intended purpose is present.
- **Consistency:** The metadata contains no contradictions and is consistent both within a dataset and between related metadata records.

Indicators based on metadata types

While the metadata quality dimensions specify which metadata properties are required, the metadata types specify which aspect of the digital object's subject matter is being measured.

A distinction is made between descriptive, provenance, source, rights, structural and technical metadata.

The distinction between metadata quality dimensions and metadata types has been made deliberately in order to separate the question of what is being assessed from the scope of the assessment, although there may be overlaps between the two. For example, authenticity is often associated with provenance metadata, and accessibility with descriptive metadata. However, these relationships are not exclusive.

In principle, any metadata quality dimension may be relevant to different types of metadata, and conversely, different quality requirements may be imposed on the same type of metadata. For example, technical metadata may be complete or consistent, whilst provenance metadata may be required to meet criteria for completeness as well as authenticity or accuracy.

Indicators based on metadata content and structure

The third dimension distinguishes between metrics based on whether they relate to the structure or the content of the metadata. Structure-related metrics concern the formal structure of the metadata, for

³³ See Prat, Nicolas and Madnick, Stuart E. Measuring Data Believability: A Provenance Approach. December 2007. MIT Sloan Research Paper No. 4672-07. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1075723>. Accessed 30 June 2026.

³⁴ Morente-Oria, Fernando. Eurostat CROS: Quality checklists for the metadata files. 24. October 2025. <https://cros.ec.europa.eu/book-page/quality-checklists-metadata-files#Timeliness%20dd>. Accessed 30 June 2026.

example the use of specific metadata elements, data types or standardized formats. Content-related metrics, on the other hand, relate to values of metadata fields, such as the required use of a controlled vocabulary or a standardized way to refer to a license.

The additional distinction between structure and content allows for a more precise description of quality metrics. Thus, the same metadata quality dimension – for example, completeness – can refer both to the presence of a required metadata element and to the completeness of its content.

5.3.2. List of Metadata Quality Indicators

Identifier	Label	Short definition	Source
MDQ-001	Accuracy	The degree to which data has attributes that correctly represent the true value of the intended attribute of a concept or event in a specific context of use.	ISO 25012
MDQ-002	Accessibility / Usability	The degree to which data has attributes that enable it to be read and interpreted by users, and are expressed in appropriate languages, symbols and units in a specific context of use.	ISO 25012
MDQ-003	Authenticity	An authentic record is one that can be proven a) to be what it purports to be, b) to have been created or sent by the person purported to have created or sent it, and c) to have been created or sent at the time purported.	ISO 15489
MDQ-004	Completeness	The degree to which subject data associated with an entity has values for all expected attributes and related entity instances in a specific context or use.	ISO 25012
MDQ-005	Consistency	The degree to which data has attributes that are free from contradiction and are coherent with other data in a specific context of use.	ISO 25012
MDQ-006	Descriptive	<i>Metadata</i> that describes an <i>Object</i> in	EDEN definition

	Metadata	such a way that people can discover, identify and understand the wider context of the <i>Object</i> today and in the future. Contains information such as information on the creator(s), title, resource type, keywords, subject(s), description/abstract, identifier(s), related items, date, language or funding reference.	
MDQ-007	Provenance Metadata	<i>Metadata</i> keeping track of the creation of the <i>Object</i> and its components, and any processes that have affected them. <i>Provenance metadata</i> is typically recorded as a series of events and agents involved in such events.	EDEN definition
MDQ-008	Source Metadata	Source metadata is descriptive and administrative metadata about the source format or media of a component of the METS object such as a digital content file. It is often used for discovery, data administration or preservation of the digital object.	METS 2 Guide ³⁵
MDQ-009	Rights Metadata	<i>Metadata</i> conveying all relevant information about the rights to retain, manipulate and reproduce the <i>Object</i> . <i>Rights metadata</i> are the serialization of rights statements in a textual, preferably machine-actionable, structured form.	EDEN definition
MDQ-010	Structural Metadata	<i>Metadata</i> storing the relationships between <i>Files</i> and logical parts, i.e., between components of the <i>Object</i> (<i>intellectual entity</i> , <i>Representation</i> , <i>File</i> , <i>Bitstream</i>).	EDEN definition

³⁵ METS 2 Guide: Describing characteristics of the source material.
https://mets.github.io/METS-guide/howto/source_metadata.html

MDQ-011	Technical Metadata	Characteristics attached to the <i>File(s)</i> or <i>Bitstreams</i> —i.e. the information carriers—rather than to the <i>Intellectual Entity</i> (the essence of the work or documentary resource). <i>Technical metadata</i> have different purposes, and cover in particular fixity (number of <i>File / Bitstreams</i> , size, checksums), file format and codecs, special or rare features, dependencies to software or hardware environment required for rendering, validity, and quality metrics (e.g., for audiovisual material, bit depth, sampling frequency, etc.).	EDEN definition
MDQ-012	Content	The information stored inside the (container) elements.	EDEN definition
MDQ-013	Structure	The arrangement of (container) elements in the metadata.	EDEN definition

6. Use Cases

To illustrate the versatility of the approach, we propose three distinct use cases. The first shows how the indicators can be embedded in a Digital Collection Development Policy. The second demonstrates their use in drafting national guidelines for the appraisal of research data in Finland. The third describes how the metrics structure will be adopted by the Data-Quality-Checker Service to harmonise reporting across TDAs. These examples highlight how the same set of indicators can serve very different organisational needs.

6.1. Elaborating A Digital Collection Development Policy

It is common practice in libraries and archives to develop collection development policies.³⁶ This practice of elaborating and publishing strategies for collection accrual is also widespread in other heritage institutions, although the resulting document sometimes bears a different name. Nevertheless, in organizations that collect both physical and digital objects, the following remarks should be made:

- Collection development policies often do not take into account born-digital collections, while the document outlining appraisal criteria for digital objects is a separately published list of accepted file formats.

³⁶ See section “Policy” in the Wikipedia page *Collection development*, available at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Collection_development#Policy. Accessed on June 26th 2026.

- As a consequence, in the case of born-digital collections, the file format serves as the primary, if not sole, appraisal criterion.
- The appraisal criteria are not formalized according to a coherent structure but are expressed in an unstructured textual form, which can introduce ambiguities.

It would therefore be useful for TDAs to use the indicators described in this document in order to formalize their collection development policy. This approach would make it possible to address both contextual and technical quality requirements simultaneously. The proposed approach is as follows:

1. The identification of a subset of relevant indicators for a given data collection project – it is important to note here that not all indicators are relevant to every context, and that the TDA teams select those that meet their specific criteria.
2. For each of these indicators, one or more metrics are developed to describe the characteristic of the object to be evaluated and the desired value(s). It should be noted that a metric is not necessarily discriminating: it is also possible to specify that, for a given characteristic, all values are acceptable.³⁷ This task can obviously draw on the examination of metrics derived from policy documents – as provided in this report – but it should not be limited to them; the discipline, industry sector, content types, and file formats will likely require the development of tailored metrics.
3. Where applicable, a description of the consequences should the stated requirements not be met: are the digital objects simply rejected? Does the TDA intervene to rectify the situation? Is the producer required to provide an alternative representation that meets these requirements? Etc.

6.2. Creating National Guidelines for the Appraisal of Research Data in Finland

The National Digital Preservation Services in Finland, funded by the Ministry of Education and Culture and developed by CSC, preserve both digital cultural heritage and research data. The services have a specification for a limited set of sustainable file formats accepted for digital preservation and a set of criteria for assessing the sustainability of file formats. This criteria will be revised in collaboration with the partner organisations that ingest data to the national services, based on the findings from this EDEN task.

The file format specifications are updated annually together with the partner organisations. New suggested file formats must be assessed according to the sustainability assessment criteria before they can be added to the specification. The specification currently includes 39 recommended and 10 accepted file formats (not including the various file format versions that are mentioned).³⁸ Recommended file formats are file formats that are considered to remain usable for a long time, whereas accepted file formats are common but not deemed archivable.

The criteria for assessing the sustainability of file formats was initially adopted from earlier reports on file format sustainability assessment, and was agreed upon nationally in Finland in 2015. The set of criteria has become slightly outdated and has proven to be particularly challenging when assessing file formats for

³⁷ The National Library of the Netherlands specifies, for example, that “it does not matter whether that publication appeared online or on paper, or who created and shared it: it could be a person, an organisation or even a machine, such as the writing robot ChatGPT.” (‘Moving with a Changing Publishing Culture: Strategy for the Formation of the National Library Collection (2024-2030)’. Collection development policy. National Library of the Netherlands, n.d. Accessed 26 June 2026.)
<https://www.kb.nl/en/file-download/download/public/9043>.

³⁸ The National Digital Preservation Services of Finland. File Formats. Version 1.14.0.
<urn:nbn:fi-fe2020100578096>

discipline specific research data. It has been clear that a new set of criteria, or a new process, is needed to facilitate digital preservation of research data in a more meaningful way.

CSC also produces National Fairdata services for management and publication of research data.³⁹ The National Digital Preservation Service for Research Data is part of the Fairdata services, providing long-term digital preservation for research data. In 2025 a new national working group, facilitated by CSC, was installed with the mandate to improve the national Fairdata services and foster better research data management in Finnish universities and research data institutions through the use and adoption of the national services. One of the areas selected for joint development was creating national guidelines for appraisal and archiving of research data. The working group had identified that the institutions struggled with identifying and selecting datasets for long-term preservation.

The first draft of the national guidelines was created late 2025 and was largely modelled on the principle of archival of research data sets as a solution for better long-term management of research data and performing appraisal when determining the viability of datasets for archiving. Four main areas, largely inspired by the appraisal and selection policy of the National Archives of Finland, were defined: a functional analysis of activities producing the data, the information value of the data, performing a cost analysis, and analysing the technical format of the data. The fourth area, technical format analysis, corresponds to the needs of the National Digital Preservation Services in Finland to create a new set of criteria for assessing the sustainability of research data. The indicators and metrics, produced by this EDEN task, will form the basis for the new criteria and methodology. This methodology will in part be integrated to the national guidelines for appraisal of research data in Finland.

6.3. Use of Metrics Structure in Data Quality Checker Service

The outcomes of the Metric Development Group will be adopted directly by the Data Quality Checker Service (DQCS). The main purpose is to enable TDAs to report the results of data quality analyses using the metrics structure intended for information objects; category, indicator, metric & requirement. This will help to ensure that reports produced by TDAs follow a consistent structure, making them easier to interpret and reuse across different TDAs that will follow the same metrics structure.

The current approach allows each TDA to select the subset of indicators and requirements that is relevant to its domain and data types, rather than requiring implementation of the full set of metrics. This flexibility in reporting is crucial for DQCS design since TDAs in the EOSC ecosystem come from a wide range of institutional, national or disciplinary domains. As a result, the approach supports easier integration with DQCS while allowing TDAs to apply metrics structure in a way that fits their specific needs.

7. Outlook and Future Work

This second milestone of task T1.2 represents the initial version of an ongoing study on the contextual, technical and metadata quality dimensions relevant to the long-term preservation of digital objects. The indicators and metrics produced by this task are intended to serve as a reference for the EDEN project across its various work packages.

³⁹ <https://www.fairdata.fi/en/>.

Specifically, they are expected to be used for the following purposes:

- To constitute a reference for the quality dimensions in the tool development endeavours within WP2, particularly the Data Quality Service;
- To structure WP3's interactions with digital preservation professionals and researchers surveyed or interviewed during the project;
- As a foundation for task T1.3, currently being launched under WP1; one key question for that task will be how the quality dimensions identified by these indicators evolve over the long term.

Additionally, they will be picked up by tasks T1.1 and T1.3 within WP1 as well as by WP2 and WP3 for stakeholder validation and maximized update. Task T3.2 is responsible for evaluating these indicators and metrics against discipline-specific needs. This work will begin in July 2026 and will help identify any potential gaps or usability issues. Extending the metrics to address the specific needs of the disciplines represented within the EDEN project is also envisaged as an outcome of this evaluation.

The methodology that produced the current indicators and linked them to implemented metrics will be extended to test and define domain-specific metrics while the explored "data-property" attributes (property, unit, level-to-reach) will undergo deeper curation and be evaluated for inclusion in the Re-Use Fitness Framework.

Finally, it should be noted that task T1.2 is charged with reviewing milestones M1.1 (Core Preservation Processes) and M1.2 (Metrics for Information Re-Use) and expanding upon them for deliverable D1.3, due in March 2027. This output will examine the relationships between the two previously developed components of the Re-Use Fitness Framework and the third component: Preservation Intention and Designated Community needs.

All of these activities feed directly into the EOSC EDEN Re-Use Fitness Framework, whose overarching goal is to identify data suitable for long-term preservation by extending FAIR and technical-quality practices with re-use-fitness metrics, a re-appraisal process, and cross-disciplinary quality requirements.